

STUDY OF EXTERNAL INFLUENCE ON OPTICAL FIBERS AND CREATION OF PRESSURE SENSORS

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Abstract. *An analysis of the development of technologies for creating highly sensitive fiber-optic sensors and studying the parameters of fiber light guides with preservation of polarization under external influence was performed. In light of the proposed hypothesis about the greater efficiency of phase modulation of light radiation in few-mode fibers than in single-mode optical fibers, the results of measurements of phase shifts under uniaxial-transverse strains performed for different sections of the fiber become obvious. The results were obtained from repeated measurements of the value of ψ depending on the force F , both in the process of increasing the load and when decreasing it. The high sensitivity of the low-mode operating mode of an optical fiber to anisotropic external influences is shown, compared with that of the single-mode operating mode of the same fiber. This result is of great practical value in the development and manufacture of highly sensitive fiber-optic sensors of various physical qualities.*

Keywords: *optical fiber, polarization, ellipticity angle, external load, reflectometric sensors.*

Introduction

The modern world is unthinkable without highly sensitive sensors, which are used in various industries, construction, technology, mining, etc. Of particular interest are sensors used in various areas of medicine. Flexible optical fibers are excellent for these purposes; owing to their small size, they can penetrate into the most inaccessible places of the human body, for example, via the vessels of the circulatory system for propagation [1].

In addition to using optical fibers to collect information about the state of the human body, it is possible to use optical fibers as channels for transmitting optical radiation to influence tissue. It is also possible to use several optical fibers in parallel, for example, to combine endoscopy with targeted (under the control of the doctor's vision) biopsy and probing [2].

Assessing the expected penetration depth of laser radiation into biological tissue is important for adequate planning and safe implementation of laser operations. Radiation with a wavelength of 1.06 μm is used to influence pathological neoplasms in the digestive tract, perform coagulation of intracavitary bleeding, and treat venous congenital defects in dermatology [3].

One of the most important characteristics of optical fibers due to their specific use in medicine is the minimum possible bending radius. This parameter is standardized by the ITU-T Recommendation G.657, according to which the minimum bending radius varies from 10 mm to 5 mm. The latter value is achievable via a relatively new optical fiber design with reduced bending losses—microstructured HAF (holed assisted fiber) fibers. These fibers implement the idea of creating a double protective barrier via nanotechnology. Around the quartz core, along the perimeter of a conventional hexagon, there are two rings of hollow air through holes, providing complete internal reflection at the quartz-air interface. The second layer is needed to reflect

radiation that partially penetrates beyond the first periodic structure. Studies have shown that with the optimal selection of the diameter of the holes and the spacing of the first and second layers, it is possible to obtain losses of less than 0.1 dB at a bend with a radius of up to 5 mm [4].

Further applications of laser fiber technology in medical technology are associated not only with the production of quartz optical fibers with a small bending radius and the development of the production of other types of flexible light guides, but also with the creation of semiconductor lasers and active optical fiber lasers. An active optical fiber, when ions of rare earth elements are introduced into its core, can be used to amplify or generate radiation. To date, technologies have been developed for activating optical fibers with rare earth elements (Ho, Tm, Er, Bi, Yb, Nd, Tb, etc.) using ion–plasma and ion–beam vacuum methods [5].

Optical fibers are very often used in medicine in the field of diagnostics. Because optical fibers are very thin, they can be spun into flexible strands and can be used in studies of blood vessels, lungs and other human organs. Fiber optic research is essential in the medical field. The scope of application of optical fibers in medical practice and research continues to grow rapidly every day [6].

Fiber Bragg grating (FBG) is one of the most commonly used elements for the development of smart medical textiles (FBG embedded in a textile bandage), because of its good sensitivity to deformation. This characteristic allows the development of many configurations, both pointially and sequentially and parallelly distributed, based on measuring the magnitude of the compression–tension deformation of the FBG when monitoring respiration, while monitoring heart rate or pulse [7].

The results of studies of low-mode optical fibers with preservation of polarization quite convincingly indicate the high sensitivity of the low-mode operating mode of an optical fiber to anisotropic external influences, compared with the single-mode operating mode of the same fiber. This result is of great practical value in the development and manufacture of highly sensitive fiber–optic sensors of various physical qualities.

Study of the polarization parameters of optical fibers under loads

We have carried out studies on the parameters of fiber light guides with preservation of polarization under external influence. Fig.1 shows the characteristic dependence of the phase shift δ or ellipticity angle ψ on the load F for uniaxial transverse deformation of a fiber light guide with length $l = 32$ mm. These dependences fit into a linear dependence within the experimental error ($\sim 1\%$), however, there is a rather significant difference in the experimental data obtained for different sections of the fiber. This difference occurs because different sections of the fiber are subject to deformation, in which the elliptical core is oriented differently relative to the direction of uniaxial transverse deformation, which leads to a difference in the phase shifts δ (or ellipticity angles ψ) for the same amount of deformation.

The maximum slope of the dependence $\psi(F)$ clearly occurs when the direction of action of the deformation and the axes of the ellipse of the fiber core coincide. According to the measurement data, the value of $d\delta(F)/dF = 0.57$ rad/N, is in good agreement (in order of magnitude) with the data of [8], where measurements of phase shifts $\delta(F)$ were carried out at significantly larger values of uniaxial transverse deformations, and our measurement data confirm the conclusion of works [8,9] about the correspondence of the measurement results $\delta(F)$ for fiber light guides with a protective plastic sheath with the results of measurements of $\delta(F)$ in fibers without a protective coating.

Notably, the results shown in Fig. 1 were obtained from repeated measurements of the value of ψ depending on the force F , both in the process of increasing the load and when decreasing it.

This figure also shows that the obtained experimental dependence ψ (F) is consistent with the theoretical dependence in the range of low loads. Note that in these measurements, the azimuth of the plane of polarization of light radiation entering the fiber light guide while maintaining polarization coincided with the azimuth of one of the axes of the light guide.

Fig. 1. Dependence of the angle of ellipticity Ψ on the magnitude of the load F for uniaxial transverse deformation of a fiber light guide 32 mm long

Fig. 2 shows the dependence of the phase shift δ on the load F [10] applied in the longitudinal direction, i.e., it is responsible for fiber stretching.

Fig. 2. Dependence of the angle of ellipticity Ψ on the load F in the longitudinal direction

The measurements were carried out for two types of fibers (with different λ_c), and in one case, the azimuth of the plane of polarization of light radiation coincided with the azimuth of one of the axes of the light guide while maintaining polarization; in the other case, an angle of 45° was used. These dependences are clearly linear in the specified load range (up to 1 N), but for a fiber with a cutoff wavelength of $\lambda_c \approx 0.6 \mu\text{m}$, the dependence $\delta(F)$ is flatter than that for a fiber with $\lambda_c > 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ [10].

This result seems quite understandable, since in the case of a cutoff wavelength of $\lambda_c > 0.6 \mu\text{m}$, the fiber light guide operates in low-mode mode (more than two modes), and it is clear that the conditions for channeling higher (in order) optical modes than in the fundamental mode, HE_{11} , strongly depend on the nature of the external influences (in particular, force) on the fiber, which leads to a sharper dependence of the phase shift on the deformation of the optical fiber.

Note that a similar situation is also observed with uniaxial transverse deformation of the fiber in Fig.1, where the dependence of $\delta(F)$ on the amplitude of uniaxial transverse strain in the case of a single-mode fiber with $\lambda_c = 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ has a significantly lower slope.

In light of the proposed hypothesis about the significantly greater efficiency of phase modulation of light radiation in low-mode fibers than in single-mode optical fibers, the results of measurements of phase shifts under uniaxial transverse strains performed for different sections of the fiber become obvious.

However, the occurrence of a phase shift between orthogonal modes when an optical fiber is twisted is especially sensitive to the operating mode of the fiber (single-mode or few-mode). At small fiber twist angles (≤ 1 deg/cm), the fiber deformation associated with elongation or transverse deformation is very small, and its contribution to the ellipticity modulation mechanism can be neglected. In this case, the orthogonal circularly polarized modes $HE_{\parallel}(+)$ and $HE_{\parallel}(-)$, channeled in the fiber core, acquire a phase difference proportional to the twist angle β , and the linearly polarized radiation undergoes rotation of the plane of polarization [11].

However, owing to the unequal nature of the attenuation of the circular modes $HE_{\parallel}(+)$ and $HE_{\parallel}(-)$ during channeling in the fiber, the transmitted light radiation is also characterized by elliptical polarization, and, in the case of a low-mode operating mode, with external influences significantly changing the conditions for the propagation of higher-order modes ($-TE_0, TM_0$, etc. – mode), the efficiency of ellipticity modulation can increase significantly compared with the induced optical activity in a single-mode operating mode.

Indeed, our results of measuring the ellipticity angle ψ with a twisted fiber (Fig. 3) showed that this is the case. Fig. 3 shows the results of measuring the phase shift δ (ellipticity angle ψ) in a low-mode fiber ($\lambda c > 0.6 \mu m$) with preservation of polarization when twisted at small angles (≤ 1 deg/cm), and it is clear that this dependence is linear in the indicated range of twist angles (measurements were performed both with an increase in the degree of fiber twist and with its decrease) [10].

Fig. 3. Dependence of the angle of ellipticity Ψ (phase shift δ) in a fiber with the preservation of polarization when it is twisted through small angles on the magnitude of the load F

The ratio of the ellipticity angle to the twist angle is $\psi/\beta \approx 1.3$, which is more than an order of magnitude greater than the similar coefficient obtained in [12,11]; when the angle of rotation of the plane of polarization of light in a twisted single-mode fiber is measured.

Research on reflectometric sensors

Amplitude fiber-optic pressure sensors (FOSs) have several advantages over strain-resistive and capacitive sensors, such as insensitivity to electromagnetic fields, fires, explosions and electrical safety. This is due to their principle of operation, which consists of the redistribution of the light flux between the emitting and receiving optical fibers due to the movement of the micromirror under the influence of the measured pressure [13–15].

The general issues of designing amplitude pressure water pumps were considered in [12–17].

The conversion characteristic of reflectometric-type amplitude pressure waveforms has the following structure:

$$U = F_3\{F_2[F_1(p)]\} \quad (1)$$

where F_1 , F_2 , and F_3 are private transformation functions that correspond to three stages of transformation: pressure into micromirror movement, micromirror movement into a change in light flux, and a change in light flux into an electrical signal; p is the measured pressure [15–20]. To date, the features of the F_2 conversion function and their influence on measurement errors have been studied in detail [15–19]. In pressure sensors, it is necessary to consider the nonlinearity of the partial conversion function F_1 and optimize the parameters of the entire optomechanical unit (fiber + micromirror), which has not yet been described in detail.

The transformation function F_1 is determined via numerical methods, and the influence of geometric parameters on the transformation function of the optomechanical unit as a whole is studied,

$$I/I_0 = F_2[F_1(p)], \quad (2)$$

where I_0 is the intensity of the light flux emerging from the emitting fiber, and I is the intensity of the light flux entering the receiving fiber.

Fig. 4 shows the design of the optomechanical unit of the device, which contains two optical fibers (emitting and receiving) and a reflecting micromirror, the normal of which is parallel to the axes of the optical fibers. In pressure sensors, the micromirror is also an elastic element (EE), which is affected by the measured pressure of the vessels.

This gives rise to a specific feature of designing a matrix of mosaic micromirrors: it is necessary to ensure maximum movement when the micromirror is deformed such that it does not exceed the maximum permissible range (Fig. 4).

We have studied the influence of external mechanical loads on low-mode optical fibers with preservation of polarization to develop mosaic multisensor fiber optic pressure sensors for medical applications. In Fig. 5 the number (1) shows a graph of changes in the optical power in the receiving fiber of the sensor depending on the distance to the mirror membrane (in mm) for a standard reflectometric sensor with separated optical channels based on two identical multimode fibers, with a core thickness of 200 μm . Number (2) indicates a graph for a new fiber-optic sensor using an emitting single-mode fiber (core diameter of 8 μm) and a receiving multimode fiber (core diameter of 200 μm), manufactured via vacuum technology.

Fig. 4. Graph of the change in the relative optical power in the receiving fiber sensor depending on the distance to the mirror membrane

The graph clearly shows that there are two quasilinear sections. First: from 1.5 mm to 3.5 mm. The second range is from 3.5 to 9 mm. The sensitivity of the sensor is a fraction of a micron. Compared with a standard fiber-optic sensor, the new sensor has 3 times greater sensitivity, significantly (more than doubled) the dynamic range, and a more linear characteristic of the dependence of the signal on the measured distance.

Conclusion

The results of studies of low-mode optical fiber optics with polarization preservation quite convincingly indicate the high sensitivity of the low-mode operating mode of an optical fiber to anisotropic external influences, compared with the single-mode operating mode of the same fiber. This result is of great practical value in the development and manufacture of highly sensitive fiber-optic sensors of various physical qualities.

The developed fiber-optic reflectometric sensors with vacuum coatings have improved characteristics and can be successfully used in a number of measurements of the moving surfaces of various objects. They allow one to read any micro profile with great accuracy (fractions of a micron) and study the vector field of micro-oscillations with great accuracy, visualizing the volumetric dynamic relief of broadband low-frequency oscillations.

Such a sensor is very convenient for use in medicine, since it literally sticks to the part of the skin being examined and allows, practically without distortion, the vibrations being studied, for example, the pulse of an artery, to be recorded. This sensor design can also be used for acoustic and hydrological studies.

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